

On the Origins of the Abramelin Operation in Islamicate Magic

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Abstract

This paper argues that the central concern of the Book of Abramelin, whereby the practitioner is enjoined to undertake an extensive ritual in order to acquire magical power through establishing a link with his personal Guardian Angel - a cornerstone of modern Western esotericism - represents a Jewish adaptation of Islamicate magical practices similar to those reflected in Fakhr al-Dīn al-Rāzī's "Hidden Secret" (al-Sirr al-Maktūm). As the Book itself claims, and independently of the later history of the manuscript, it is plausible that the topos for this development was Mamluk Egypt in the first part of the 15th century. Basing himself on al-Rāzī's ideas, or on practices derived from them, we suggest that a Jewish magician designed a ritual aimed at acquiring the equivalent of al-Rāzī's Perfect Nature (al-Ṭibā al-Tāmm) drawing on Second Temple priestly rites and Sufi devotional practices or their Jewish analogues, and expressing the whole in terms characteristic of Jewish piety. This astonishingly fecund instance of cross-cultural transmission offers fresh insight into medieval magical borrowings from Islamicate practices.

Introduction

Notwithstanding its foundational significance to Western esotericism, scholarly research into the so-called *Book of Abramelin* has been very limited to date. The *Abramelin*, in its canonical form acquired by the time of the earliest 1608 Wolfenbüttel manuscript, recounts the story of a Jew from the Palatinate who travels to Egypt in search of magical wisdom. There he is introduced to a procedure whereby a diligent practitioner can acquire a personal relationship with his Guardian Angel which equips him with magical power and the means of its ethical deployment in the world. The Book claims (in what is an evident literary trope) to preserve these instructions to the benefit of the author's younger son, Lamech. The *dénouement* of the Operation is accompanied by a binding of demonic potentates in the service of the newly minted Magician, characteristic of the medieval European grimoire tradition. The four-part manuscript also conserves a spellbook, presented as applicable even in the absence of the Operation, and a section on magic squares, which presupposes success in it.

Scholarly debate, to the extent there has been any, has focused on the question of whether or not the text was authentically Jewish. Gershom Scholem initially inclined to this view due to the author's "*uncommon command of Hebrew*", but later revised his opinion noting Christian influences and the lack of a "*strict parallel*" to the Book in kabbalistic literature¹. For Carlos Gilly, the book was to be located in a proto-Rosicrucian current of thought, its composition dating from not much earlier than 1608². More recently, Rick-Arne Kollatsch has argued on

¹ "Alchemie und Kabbala", in *Monatsschrift für Geschichte und Wissenschaft des Judentums*, Vol. 69, 1925, pp. 95f.; *Kabbalah*, Jerusalem 1974, p. 186

² *Adam Haslmayr: der erste Verkünder der Rosenkreuzer*, Amsterdam: In de Pelikaan, 1994, p. 134

the same lines, seeing in the text numerous apparent dependencies both on a late 16th century multilingual Hebrew lexicon and on the text of the Luther Bible³.

Scholem's view, however, was based on recensions of the text which inarguably display extensive Rosicrucianizing tendencies and it also predates important research into Jewish traditions in the Islamicate world, which very well might have caused him to rethink his conclusions. More generally, a text-critical approach to the manuscript history - beyond the scope of this article - offers grounds to question the status of even the 1608 manuscript as a straightforward witness to the *Urschrift*. Kollatsch has convincingly shown that the Lutherizing standardization of Biblical citations was present in the earliest attested tradition, and dissimulated by later copyists, though whether this was intended to mask the origins is open to doubt: I am more inclined to view it as a typical esoteric strategy. More importantly, however, careful study of the word squares conclusively shows that they must have been composed after 1595, as Kollatsch argues, and the wisdom/secret dichotomy in the text is similarly also to be ascribed to the influence of Pico della Mirandola, although otherwise the text shows limited affinity with Pico's thought.

This notwithstanding, a thematic approach to the text casts it in quite a different light as it is a highly unusual synthesis of very diverse traditions. Moreover, whilst its Rosicrucian reception has undeniably been a key feature of its later development, a "proto-Rosicrucian" character of the text, even in its canonical form, is an unjustifiably audacious hypothesis: its

³ Kollatsch, Rick-Arne, *Des Abraham von Worms Buch der wahren Praktik von der alten Magie: Ein als jüdisch fingierter Magietext des frühen 17. Jahrhunderts*, 2021

possible influence on Rosicrucian *topoi*, such as the initiatory journey of Christian Rosencreutz, is much more plausibly in the other direction.

This being so, it is worthwhile to consider the plausibility of the origin story recounted by the Book itself, or at least the circumstances to which it gives a literary or exemplary form. Islamicate parallels to the material in parts two and four of the *Abramelin* (the spells and the magic squares) are plentiful and obvious, but we will here focus on the framing of Abraham's magical quest in book one together with the Operation itself, the most characteristic and apparently innovative sections of the Book as it has come down to us.

On the plausibility of an Egyptian Jewish matrix

It is hard to dispute that the piety of the Book is characteristically Jewish and that it shows a level of familiarity with - and respect for - Jewish cultural forms which would be remarkable on the part of a Christian author. This, presumably, is what inclined Scholem initially to view it as indeed Jewish in origin. At the same time, there are a number of features of the text which set it apart from a Rhineland Jewish milieu and imbue it with an apparent originality with which scholars have so far failed to come to grips. The central notion of the text, that magical potency and legitimacy in its exercise depend on a qualifying experience of spiritual purification, is unparalleled in any other medieval Christian or Jewish source, and places it in a category of its own: the magical equivalent of a linguistic isolate. At the same time, it shows little interest in Rabbinic tradition or in anything we would today term Kabbalah (much as it protests the contrary).

Instead, it occupies a very different thought world. There are no “tricks” to reach the goal of the Operation such as the ecstatic practices and letter mysticism of the Sufis or of Abulafia or Kabbalistic esoteric hermeneutics; it suffices to be pure of heart, to repent of sin, and to seek the divine face earnestly. It is also shorn of all philosophical pretensions and is characterised by a simplicity which has ensured its enduring appeal. The notion of the Guardian Angel itself sits awkwardly in a Jewish context, whereas although never an official doctrine of the Church it has been a popular notion in Christianity since the time of Jerome. The attested scribal tradition most likely derives it from this source, though it remains open that the original author may have preferred another term. It is believable enough that the author was an Ashkenazi Jew interested in magical practices and perhaps part of a broader magical fraternity: but clearly he has introduced ideas into his text which go far beyond such a putative formative milieu.

A number of these ideas are easier to situate in the milieu of Jewish piety in Mamluk Egypt, a subject which has attracted increased scholarly attention since the pioneering work of Paul Fenton⁴ and, more recently, Elisha Russ-Fishbane⁵. Abraham, the son of the seminal Jewish Neo-Aristotelian philosopher Moses Maimonides, sought to renew both public and private devotional practice in the Jewish community in Egypt by drawing on ideas and practices which were developed in the wake of the Sufi flowering encouraged by Mamluk policies following the fall of Baghdad to the Mongols in 1258. In doing so, with only partial success, he encountered a great deal of opposition from conservative quarters, showing how radical

⁴ See for instance *Deux traités de mystique juive: Obadyah Maimonides et David Maimonides*, Lagrasse: Éditions Verdier, 1987.

⁵ *Judaism, Sufism, and the Pietists of Medieval Egypt: A Study of Abraham Maimonides and his Times*, Oxford: OUP, 2015

some of these practices appeared to be from a traditional rabbinic perspective. These practices included supererogatory and ecstatic prayer, extensive withdrawal into solitude, and a concern, at times obsessive, for personal salvation which trumped the more practical considerations of the community. Maimonides *filis* believed that the Sufis had conserved prophetic traditions which they had acquired from the Jews in antiquity and to which they now bore better witness than the community itself. The recovery of these traditions he saw as having messianic import. The Cairo Genizah bears ample witness to the interest of the Jewish community in Sufi ideas at the time.

Although, by virtue of its association with the Maimonides family line and the leadership of the community, this flavor of Jewish piety is better documented (even though it too was soon eclipsed by Kabbalah and by more orthodox Rabbinic traditions), it is evident that both the Jewish community in Egypt and its wider Islamicate, including Coptic, context remained characterized by a range of popular magical ideas. On the Islamic side these are borne witness to by al-Buni's *Shams al-Ma'arif* and by the text later known in the Latin West as the *Picatrix*, as well as by numerous tractates by Sufi and other Islamic scholars on subjects such as letter and number mysticism, which are certainly also the matrix for later Kabbalistic ideas. The extent of the debt which Western esotericism owes to these sources scarcely needs further elaboration.

We therefore have evidence for a Jewish spiritual and magical milieu in Egypt in the period claimed by the *Abramelin* for the initiatory journey of its author which share a number of key characteristics with that Book and serve to illuminate some of the ways in which it differs relative to what one might have anticipated within an exclusively Ashkenazi context. Whilst

Egypt was a focal point in incubating these ideas, they could also have reached Western European Jewish circles through key Northern Mediterranean centers such as Venice and rump Byzantium: places which the author tells us he visited on his journeys.

Suggestive as this is, however, it still leaves many features of the text unelucidated. Certainly, the necessary as well as concomitant secrecy of magical groups in this period and later are sufficient to explain both the absence of more direct evidence for the specific practices attested by the *Abramelin* and the limited testimony to comparable practices in the putatively formative Islamicate milieu. This is a typical characteristic of the evidence on the transmission of magical practices more generally, and therefore cannot invalidate what is, at least, a less unsatisfactory hypothesis than the alternatives. However, it so happens that we do have evidence of a striking parallel in the Islamicate magical literature to the core precept of the *Abramelin*, which has largely been neglected to date, namely al-Rāzī's *The Hidden Secret*. This similarity is compelling enough to exclude the possibility of a parallel development and therefore requires us to posit some form of formal dependency via, at the least, a shared tradition.

Al-Rāzī and the *Hidden Secret*

Fakhr al-Dīn al-Rāzī (1149-1209) was an Ash'arī Sunni scholar from, as his name indicates, the ancient city of Rayy (Rhages), which is now part of modern Tehran. His primary concern was to bridge the gap between Avicennan philosophy and Islamic revelation. His *Hidden Secret* (Al-Sirr al-Maktūm) is an early work in which he endeavored to provide a philosophical underpinning to the operation of magic as witnessed to in the practices of the

(Harranian) Sabians. The text remains untranslated, but has been the subject of an exhaustive recent study by Michael-Sebastian Noble⁶.

Although it is frequently imagined in the Western tradition that the Hermetic sciences were resurrected during the Renaissance exclusively from manuscripts preserved by Byzantine scribes, in fact the figure of Hermes, as an antediluvian prophet identified with Enoch and with the minor Quranic figure of Idris, was central to the claims and practices of the Harranian Sabians throughout the early Middle Ages. Bar Hebraeus (1226-1286) tells us in his *Chronicon Syriacum* that “*the Sabians, who are in Harran, worship the stars and the heavenly bodies, but they confess one God who is above all. They honour Hermes, whom they call Marilaha, as their prophet, and they say that he revealed unto them the wisdom of the heavens and the knowledge of divine things*”⁷. This aligns with the picture painted by al-Rāzī and the general understanding of Hermes in the Islamicate world⁸.

The concept of the Perfect Nature (*al-Ṭibā al-Tāmm*) is known to us from multiple Islamicate sources. Al-Rāzī appears to have derived his philosophical presentation thereof from the thought of Abū'l-Barakāt (c.1080-1164/5)⁹, for whom the Perfect Nature, according to Henry Corbin, presides over a soul or group of souls, in whose regard he “*assumes a particular sollicitude and tenderness; it is he who initiates them into knowledge, protects them, guides*

⁶ Noble, Michael-Sebastian, *Philosophising the Occult: Avicennan Psychology and 'The Hidden Secret' of Fakhr al-Dīn al-Rāzī*, 2021, De Gruyter

⁷ *The Chronography of Gregory Abū'l Faraj, the Son of Aaron, the Hebrew Physician Commonly Known as Bar Hebraeus*, tr. Wallis Budge, Ernest A., 2 vols., Oxford University Press, 1932, p. 47. (Note that Bar Hebraeus, despite his epithet, was a Syriac Christian bishop, and not Jewish; Wallis Budge's title is therefore erroneous.)

⁸ Noble, p. 8; Van Bladel, Kevin, *The Arabic Hermes: from Pagan Sage to Prophet of Science*, Oxford University Press, 2009.

⁹ Noble, *op. cit.*, p.11, n.29

*them, defends them, comforts them, brings them success [...]. It is this friend, this defender and protector, who in religious language is referred to as the Angel*¹⁰. Although the concept of the Guardian Angel is hardly attested in Judaism, and may seem somewhat foreign to it, it should be recalled that Abū'l-Barakāt was himself Jewish, converting to Islam only late in life. As such, it is not to be excluded that some of his erstwhile co-religionaries were prepared to follow him on this point. Indeed, since this concept is scarcely better at home in traditional Islamic belief, one wonders to which precise religious tradition Abū'l-Barakāt is here alluding.

Suhrawardī, the noted Persian Illuminationist who was just five years al-Rāzī's junior and shared with him a common teacher, endorsed a similar concept of the perfected man possessed of occult power¹¹.

In the Latin *Picatrix*, which translates (after a fashion) the Arabic *Ghāyat al-Hakīm* (c. 950-970 CE) we read that “*Natura perfecta est spiritus philosophi, qui regit animam suam... Est forma sua in caelestis ordine, quae dat ei sapientiam et virtutem*”¹² (“The perfect Nature is the philosopher’s spirit, which governs his soul... It is his form in the celestial order, which gives him wisdom and virtue”). However, the *Picatrix* does not foresee a transformational union with the Perfect Nature, but rather a transactional one. It lacks not only the philosophical sophistication given the concept by al-Rāzī, namely the creation of the noetic

¹⁰ Corbin, *L'imagination créatrice dans le soufisme d'Ibn 'Arabi*, 1958, pp. 54f., my trans.; see also Noble, *op. cit.*, p. 81.

¹¹ Noble, *op. cit.*, pp. 267f.

¹² Pingree, David (ed.), *Picatrix: The Latin Version of the Ghāyat al-Hakīm*. Studies of the Warburg Institute, Vol. 39. London: The Warburg Institute, 1986, pp. 94f.

bond, but also the specific notions in the *Abramelin* of a qualifying Operation and of an ethical conditionality. Even if it is clear, therefore, that the concept in the *Picatrix* derives from similar roots it seems insufficient to ground the audacious architecture of the Abramelin Operation. In this regard, al-Rāzī bears witness to a plausible missing link in the chain of transmission.

In al-Rāzī's account, the unification with the Perfect Nature is, for the Sabian magician, a precondition of the ritual of ascent which presupposes the mastery of the seven planets. Although the general characteristics of ones Perfect Nature may be deduced from astrological considerations or even introspection, the invocation of the same requires asceticism and single-minded devotion. Provided this purification is carried out diligently, however, and as in the *Abramelin*, the Perfect Nature “will inevitably appear to him”¹³.

The process of purification which permits the acquisition of occult power through unification with the Perfect Nature presupposes for the Sabians extended periods of fasting and a vegan diet¹⁴. Similarly in the *Abramelin*, the adept should, during the last semester, take only pap and water, attributing this to the example of the prophet Daniel, though the latter's rigors were not as restrictive¹⁵. Garments of pure white are recommended, as in the *Abramelin*, whilst also yellow and pink are appropriate, as symbols of joy; this is the case for the second robe in the *Abramelin* as well¹⁶, and this detail is noteworthy since it departs from the Priestly model otherwise relied upon to structure the Operation.

¹³ Noble, *op. cit.*, pp. 96f.

¹⁴ Noble, *op. cit.*, pp. 161-3

¹⁵ See Dan. 10:3

¹⁶ III.9; III.11; cf Noble, *op. cit.*, pp. 164-7

Unsurprisingly, the *Abramelin* is having none of the doctrine of planetary influences, but it is sufficiently aware of the habitual association as to inveigh strongly and at length against it¹⁷. It is not hard to imagine that it may have been unwelcome also to many Islamic adepts who nevertheless also sought after the powers that such noesis was believed to mediate and enable - although al-Rāzī himself seems never to have renounced this idea.

Al-Rāzī also develops, and makes his own, the notion whereby the Perfect Nature is not only a source of power and a bridge between the noetic realm and the material which is technically needed in order to bring about magical results, defined as exceptions to the normal material order, but is also the origin of the human soul and its spiritual and philosophical guide¹⁸, a concept amply reflected in the *Abramelin* as well, and with illustrious classical roots.

In *The Hidden Secret*, to judge, at least, from Noble, the ontological primacy of the union with the Perfect Nature is not unambiguously spelled out; it is possible that al-Rāzī is riffing on Avicennan notions whilst the *realexistierende* Sabians are acting in a way more akin to what the *Picatrix* describes. However, in his later work, *al-Maṭālib al-‘Āliya min al-‘Ilm al-Ilāhī* (Exalted Topics of Inquiry within Divine Science, 1209 CE), al-Rāzī develops this idea into a “*personal soteriology for a spiritual, intellectual elite, who, by means of connection with their individual perfect natures, can complete their own epistemological ascent through the ontological hierarchy of reality, to attain certainty in metaphysical truths and realise the*

¹⁷ III.6

¹⁸ Noble, *op. cit.*, p. 25

perfection of philosophy"¹⁹. If there was any doubt, therefore, al-Rāzī by the end of his life indeed held to a doctrine of transformational noesis, which by implication, at least, conferred occult powers.

The certain knowledge of the Perfect Nature can, for al-Rāzī, not be deduced from philosophical considerations alone, but only derived from personal gnosis acquired through spiritual exertions similar to those practised by the Sufis²⁰.

The question of course arises of the reception of these ideas in later Islamicate milieux. We have as yet no direct evidence of magical practices aimed at invoking the Perfect Nature, and Sufi practices oriented towards the attainment of sainthood and prophecy, no doubt under the influence of radical Islamic monotheism, do not, to my knowledge, entertain this concept, compatible as it may seem to be with ibn 'Arabi's (1165-1240) account of divine self-revelation. The latter is nevertheless worthy of mention insofar as it lends further weight to the plausibility of the existence of communities explicitly targeting this goal or conceiving of what they were doing in this way.

In the *Meccan Revelations*, Ibn 'Arabi writes: "*For every human being, there is a spiritual reality (rūḥāniyya) from the world of command ('ālam al-amr) that is its overseer and guide, particular to it alone*"²¹. He further states that "*Every individual has a specific reality in the unseen that belongs to him alone, which governs him and from which he draws his*

¹⁹ Noble, *op. cit.*, p. 229

²⁰ Noble, *op. cit.*, pp. 243-5

²¹ *Futuhat al-Makkiyya*, ch. 8 (ed. Chodkiewicz, tr. Chittick and Morris, Pir Press 2002)

existence”²². He connects this to the *Insan al-Kamil* (Perfect Human) archetype, where each soul has a celestial reflection or "lordly presence" (*ḥaḍra rabbāniyya*) that mirrors its potential perfection. In the *Bezels of Wisdom*, he states that “*each created being is related to God only as being its particular Lord, since its relationship to the All is impossible [...] Thus, from the totality [of divine aspects] each being is assigned one particularly suited to be its Lord*”²³. This notwithstanding, an explicit angelomorphosis or angelophany bearing occult powers is (perhaps understandably) not a focus of his expositional efforts in the surviving texts.

The extent of the manuscript tradition relating to the *Hidden Secret* has not been fully established but it is plausible, as is certainly the case of the *Abramelin*, that it was privately copied by persons desirous of attaining to the gnosis and powers it describes, attesting to the likelihood of an underground circulation in support of ritual activity pursuing the aim of transformational noesis, possibly also as an interpretation of praxis openly engaged in by adepts as part of Sufi *tariqas* or as a supplement to such practices.

A Jewish ritual to the same end

Having painted a picture of a plausible Islamicate background to the idea of the Operation and the powers attendant upon it, what did the author of the *Abramelin* (or his own source) do with it?

²² *ibid.*, ch. 73

²³ Fusus, ch. 7, p. 106 (tr. R.W. Wilson, Paulist Press, 1980)

As has been noted, the Operation is extensively patterned on Jewish second temple priestly ritual, often down to the smallest details²⁴. The adept assumes the role of the Levitic High Priest as described in the Priestly Source of the Torah. Whatever Islamicate practices may have predated it, this is an audacious but fitting transformation of them with enormous resonance for a Jewish audience, as well as a great deal of controversy. The resultant practices differ in significant ways from Sufi analogues, and all of these differences are explicable as an adaptation to a Jewish milieu. The author, notwithstanding his lofty pretensions, is clearly a pious Jew and his piety shines throughout the text.

He also shows no real knowledge of Zoharic Kabbalah, despite the key importance in the text of the contrast between Kabbalah and Magic, which evidently serves the purpose of an apologia for the Book to an audience attuned to the former and inclined to grant it authority. The lack of any reference in the book to key Kabbalistic concepts is a strong argument to ground it in the Egyptian Pietist tradition, which resisted Kabbalah for a long time before it was eclipsed by it, and the insistence, nevertheless, on the superior importance of the Kabbalah only reinforces this impression. The attribution to the younger son, Lamech, may also constitute an admission of the Islamicate origins of the material, as is suggested by the reference to Isaac and Ishmael in I.9.

The assertion of a Jewish core to the ritual need not exclude Christian layers and influences, even at an early date. The text as we have it cannot merely be a slavish adaptation of an Islamicate model and aspects of its redactional and reception history prior to the 17th century remain to be elucidated. This is so particularly in relation to the spirit hierarchies, which draw

²⁴ See footnotes to the relevant sections in Kollatsch, *op. cit.*

on earlier European traditions which characteristically order such spirits into feudal ranks, a notion quite alien to Islamicate thought. It may be that the tradition in the form that Abraham encountered it still involved binding of planetary forces or their corresponding angels, a perfectly plausible Islamicate hypothesis (and one with which one imagines Christian magicians would have had little problem either) but one which Abraham would have rejected. This he would then have replaced with a model closer to home, or the specifics of the bindings may have been added subsequently.

It is entirely possible that these practices were incubated in situations of close Jewish-Christian contact between magicians open to learning from Islamicate practices, such as Venice prior to 1516, which took in many Jews fleeing the pogroms of 1349 in the Rhineland. The city plays an important role in Abraham's account: he says that he stopped off there with "*the Brothers, of whom a number recognized me by means of signs*"²⁵, seeming to imply that he was the envoy of a secret magical fraternity specifically looking for efficacious ways of achieving transformational noesis and magical power; he also tells us that similar efforts were underway in a variety of locations in Europe.

Conclusion

Viewed from a Western perspective, the *Book of Abramelin* has been difficult to classify, seeming to arise from nowhere with its daunting Operation promising to confer extraordinary powers on the adept who is intrepid enough to undertake it and to bring it to completion. We

²⁵ I.A. "*und kehret Ich ein bey den Brüdern, deren etliche durch wahrZeichen [Lo3: Wortzeichen] mich wol erkannten*".

have argued in this article that this notion has compelling Islamicate precedents which support a plausible origin in Egyptian Jewish magical circles, as the text asserts. This evidence completes inferences which may be made based on the second and fourth books, beyond the scope of this article but which argue in a similar direction, and allows us to relate it to a living tradition of ritual transformational noesis, born witness to in al-Rāzī's account of Sabian talismanic practices and thereby reaching back to notions of the personal daimon developed in late Greco-Roman Antiquity.

This is an important clarification. Whilst Proclus (412-485 CE) sees the personal daimon as “*the guardian of our life, leading us to virtue and the contemplation of the divine, if we heed its guidance*”²⁶, he is adamant that “*the daimon's function is to elevate, not to empower the soul with external forces*”²⁷. The *paredros* in the PGM is a force that the magician can bind, not one that is ontologically linked to him. For Iamblichus, gods or daimons can be invoked to confer power and effect magical operations, but the personal daimon does not play this role. It follows that we seem to be dealing here with a notion which indeed developed in the Islamicate world along the lines described by al-Rāzī and perhaps enriched by his own contribution.

²⁶ Commentary on Plato's *Alcibiades I*, 104c, trans. O'Neill

²⁷ *op. cit.*, 79